

**Extract from Protocol No. 3
of the Scientific Council Meeting
Institute of Philosophy of ANAS
dated June 12, 2020**

Heard: Discussion of the monograph by Senior Research Fellow of the Sociology Department, Doctor of Philosophical Sciences A.A. Alizade titled “Gasification and Operation of the Gas Economy in Azerbaijan (1955–1970). Historical-Sociological Aspect”.

Resolved:

1. Recommend the monograph “Gasification and Operation of the Gas Economy in Azerbaijan (1955–1970). Historical-Sociological Aspect” by Senior Research Fellow of the Sociology Department, Doctor of Philosophical Sciences A.A. Alizade for publication.
2. Approve Professor Rafail Musa oghlu Hasanov, Doctor of Sociological Sciences, as the scientific editor.

Scientific Secretary: (Signature) **S.A. Hasanova**

Seal: (Official stamp of the Institute)